

HEALTHY TOURISM DEVELOPMENT POLICY IN REALIZING SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN INDONESIA

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Abstract

A healthy tourism development policy is a form of government interference in maintaining the function of public goods to realize sustainable development. This study aims to determine the targets and achievements of tourism area development and analyze the priorities of the synthesis of healthy tourism development in Banyuwangi Regency, East Java, Indonesia. This study analyzes the targets and achievements of health tourism and the Analytic Network Process (ANP). The results of the analysis showed that the results of the perception of expert respondents stated that macro-tourism in Banyuwangi had reached the target of healthy tourism by 82.5%, and the results of the priority synthesis of healthy tourism development in Banyuwangi on the criteria of objects and tourist attractions of 0.16242 with Kendall's coefficient of concordance W (rate agreement) with a high value. The government plays a vital role in the development of health tourism, and healthy tourism areas will be able to realize sustainable development.

Keywords: Policy, Healthy Tourism, Banyuwangi Regency Indonesia.

1. INTRODUCTION

The neoclassical economic view is that an economic actor decides what he will do rationally. However, both have beliefs about market mechanisms. In this case, the basis of their assumptions is optimal market mechanisms through several assumptions: entire competition, utility-maximizing, and price equilibrium formed through the impulse between demand and supply in the market (Luithlen, 1993).

Some views stand out in the traditions of classical and neoclassical thought on the role of government in the economy. As in the tradition of classical and neo-classical, considered to limit government role (Smith, 1776), some experts, such as (Blommestein & Steunenberg, 2015), state that there are paradoxical conditions where the government has a significant role in the economy, but theoretically, the highest goal of the economy is to reduce the role of the authorities.

As in Keynesian thought (Spithoven, 2017), government intervention is indispensable in times of crisis, especially crises, due to the non-fulfilment of assumptions in classical economic thinking, such as full employment and uneven distribution of income (Keynes, 1973a). In the Keynesian tradition, the existence of recession is the fruit of widespread market failure. In these conditions, the Keynesian group can provide space scientifically about government

intervention in the economy, such as monetary policy and countercyclical fiscal policy (Priyono & Ismail, 2012).

Environmentalists use the term sustainability to clarify the most desirable balance between economic growths on the one hand and the preservation of the environment or natural resources on the other. Although the definition is quite a lot, the term sustainable refers to "meeting the needs of the present generation without harming future generations" (Todaro, 2006: 564).

The condition of world tourism has undergone drastic changes due to the Covid-19 pandemic; the barometer of world tourism in 2020 shows that there was a decrease of around one billion international arrivals worldwide last year compared to 2019 because of travel restrictions imposed by almost every country to control the Corona pandemic (UNWTO, 2020)

The condition of foreign tourists in Indonesia 2020 who entered Indonesia was only around 4.052 million people, or about 25% of the number of tourists who entered Indonesia in 2019. Various efforts were made to save Indonesian tourism. There are three phases of the "rescue" carried out by the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy/Tourism and Creative Economy Agency (Kemenparekraf / Baparekraf): Emergency Response, Recovery, and Normalization (Kemenparekraf, 2021).

Figure 1: Statistical Graph of Mancanaegara Tourist Visits (in the scale of thousand) for 2018-2020 in Indonesia (Source: Kemenparekraf, 2021)

Based on data from the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy (2021), there is a significant decrease in the number of local and foreign tourists. The total number of foreign tourist visits to Indonesia in 2020 was 4.02 million. Compared to 2019, the number of foreign tourists decreased by 75.03 percent. Based on their nationality, five countries visited Indonesia the most in 2020: Timor Leste, Malaysia, Singapore, Australia, and China. Most of those countries are neighbouring countries, except for China.

The country's foreign exchange receipts from the tourism sector also decreased dramatically. According to the Minister of Tourism and Creative Economy, Sandiaga Uno, on the Republika.co.id website, the projected foreign exchange receipts from tourism in 2020 are between 4-7 billion U.S. dollars. Before the pandemic, tourism foreign exchange receipts in 2020 were targeted at US\$ 19-21 billion. Compared to 2019, the decline was quite significant

because tourism foreign exchange receipts in the previous year almost reached 20 billion U.S. dollars (Kemenparekraf, 2021).

Figure 2: Statistical Chart of Mancanaegara Tourist Visits for 2020-2021 in Indonesia (Source: Kemenparekraf, 2022)

Based on statistical data, tourist visits to Indonesia through all entrances in December 2021 amounted to 163,619 visits or a decrease of -0.28% compared to tourist visits in December 2020, which amounted to 164,079 visits. Meanwhile, based on nationality, the number of tourist visits in December 2021 at all entrances recorded the highest number of visits from Timor Leste, amounting to 84,975 visits, Malaysia with 48,728 visits, Papua New Guinea with 4,880 visits, China with 4,513 visits, and Russia with 2,324 visits.

Tourism potential in Banyuwangi first received an award from the United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) in the "12th UNWTO Awards Forum" competition in Madrid, Spain, in January 2016. Banyuwangi was awarded the "UNWTO Awards for Excellence and Innovation in Tourism" in the category of "Public Policy Innovation and Governance," superior to other nominees from Colombia, Kenya, and Puerto Rico (Bappeda, 2016).

The Banyuwangi Tourism Office recorded that annual visits by national and foreign tourists in Banyuwangi experienced an increase from 2013 to 2019. However, unlike the previous years, tourism visits in Banyuwangi in 2020 and 2021 experienced a contraction in the growth of tourist visits, both foreign and domestic, due to the widespread Covid-19 outbreak in Banyuwangi.

Figure 3: Statistical Graph of the Number of Domestic Tourist Visits in 2013-2021 in Banyuwangi Regency (Source: Disbudpar, 2022)

In 2020 the number of domestic tourist visits experienced a decrease of -43.10%, and in 2021 it was -38.32%.

Figure 4: Statistical Graph of the Number of Foreign Tourist Visits in 2013-2021 in Banyuwangi Regency (Source: Disbudpar, 2022)

In 2020, the number of foreign tourist visits experienced a growth of -73.21%, and in 2021 about -85.84%. Various awards, an increase in per capita income from the tourism sector, and an increase in the number of visitors are among the achievements in the tourism sector. However, due to the international disaster with the rampant Covid-19, there was a decrease in the number of visitors and PAD from the tourism sector.

Based on this phenomenon, the role of government intervention is essential for overcoming the problems faced by the tourism sector in Banyuwangi, in particular, how to make the tourism sector survive and be sustainable in supporting sustainable economic development in Banyuwangi. It is crucial to create a tourism situation that can maintain environmental health sustainability so that it is not polluted, provides amenities, and a vital institution manages the destination.

Referring to the above phenomenon, variables in research on the development of health tourism that will survive in various situations with concerns on 1) Tourism and Health Information, 2) Tourism Facilities, 3) Tourism Objects and Attractions, 4) Health Services, 5) Supporting Facilities, and 6) Community so that efforts in the development of health tourism are optimally carried out in Banyuwangi. Prioritization of healthy tourism policy development in Banyuwangi was studied using network process (ANP) analytics techniques. Therefore, this research is concerned with the theme of Healthy Tourism Development Policy in Realizing Sustainable Development under the sustainable development goals (SDGs) indicators.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Neoclassical Economic Theory

Neoclassical economic theory is considered one of the mainstream economies in the world is the neoclassical economic theory (Dequech, 2007) and has become the basis of the foothold of the majority of economic thought in the history of economic thought in the world (Agboola, 2015). Neoclassical economic theory is an Economic of Thought influenced by classical economic flows (Smith, 1776), especially concerning market mechanisms as one of the mechanisms considered the most efficient in allocating resources in the economy (Inoua & Smith, 2021).

This basis of belief about market mechanisms later received much criticism, especially about the concept that is considered a real danger to the ecological system, one of the concepts about economic growth and Gross Domestic Product (Daly & Farley, 2010) as one the figures of the ecological economy as a dangerous concept. Hence, it needs to be replaced with other concepts. Although it received much criticism, this concept also received much support, considering that the market mechanism would naturally make corrections to environmental degradation at an early stage would occur which would then occur adjustments after environmental degradation experienced a turning point (Grossman & Kruger, 1992) which formulated a hypothesis known as Environmental Kuznets Curves which is analogous to (Kuznets, 1955).

In the Keynesian tradition of thought (Spithoven, 2017), government intervention is indispensable in times of crisis, especially crises, due to the non-fulfilment of assumptions in classical economic thought such as full employment and uneven income distribution (Keynes, 1973). Although there is much opposition from the ecological economy, for Neoclassic Economic circles, the concept of Gross Domestic Product and Economic Growth environmental issues do not need to get intervention from the government but will naturally make adjustments along with the higher income of the community with changes in behavior that occur in society (Simon, 1996). This condition to the study conducted by (Grossman & Kruger, 1992) suggests that conformity to healthy and suitable environmental conditions will occur when environmental degradation has reached a turning point.

2.2 Institutional Economics

One of the branches of economic science that gives a lot of criticism and challenge to neoclassical is institutional economics. One of the foundations of Classical Institutionalism is Thorstein Veblen, Wesley Mitchell, and John R. Commons (Rutherford, 2001), but the influence of Thorstein Veblen is seen to be enormous compared to others. Despite being a critic, both neoclassical and institutional economics have a point of commonality, especially regarding the role of government in the provision of public goods and the handling of externality issues of the production process (Cetin, 2012). One of the rationally acceptable economic arguments on the issue of public goods and externalities is the idea of market mechanisms not being able to produce public goods and not being able to o

Institutions are rules of the games that exist in society, more fully than institutions are present to regulate the deviant behavior of human beings (North, 1990, 1991). Whereas (Yeager, 1999) also defines institutions as rules of the games that exist in society and regulate human interactions in them, institutions have a function of reducing uncertainty in interactions through the existence of patterns regulated in the rules of the games. As for how the institution is tangible, at least four forms of institutions exist, including formal rules, informal rules, and mechanisms for enforcing these rules. A different definition was put forward by (Greif, 1998), which defines institutions as enforcement to reach a point of equilibrium.

2.3 Sustainable Development Theory

Regional economic development is a process by which local governments and their communities manage existing resources and form a pattern of a partnership between local authorities and the private sector to create new jobs and stimulate the development of economic activity (economic growth) within the region (Arsyad, 1999: 108).

Todaro & Smith (2003) stated that the success of a country's economic development is shown by three central values, namely (1) the development of people's ability to meet their basic needs (sustenance), (2) the increasing sense of self-esteem of society as a human being, and (3) the increasing ability of society to choose (freedom from servitude) which is one of the human rights.

These core values correspond to what was put forward by Amartya Sen (1999: 3) – winner of the 1998 Nobel Prize in Economics – that 'development can be seen, it is argued here, as a process of expanding the fundamental freedoms that people enjoy. Finally, it was realized that the definition of economic development is comprehensive, not just how to increase GNP per year. Economic development is multidimensional and includes various aspects of people's lives, not just one aspect (economy). Economic development can be defined as any activity carried out by a country to develop economic activities and the standard of living of its people. With these limitations, economic development can generally be defined as a process that causes an increase in the real income per capita of a country's population in the long term, accompanied by improvements to the institutional system.

2.4 Public Policy Theory

Hogwood and Lewis (1984) generally classify policies into three groups: 1) The policy-making process is a formulation activity until the creation of a policy. 2) The implementation process is the implementation of policies that have been formulated. 3) The policy evaluation process is the process of reviewing the implementation that has been implemented or, in other words looking for answers to what happened as a result of the implementation of specific policies and discussing the methods used and the results achieved. According to Dunn (2000), the process of policy analysis is a set of activities in the process of activities of a political nature. Political activity is defined as a policy-making process and visualized as a series of interdependent stages, namely: 1) Agenda preparation, 2) Policy formulation, 3) Policy adoption, 4) Policy implementation, and 5) Policy assessment.

2.5 Tourism

It is related to tourism development, Law Number 10 of 2009 concerning tourism. Article 4 states the objectives of tourism to 1) Increase economic growth; 2) Improve the welfare of the people; 3) Eliminate poverty; 4) Addressing unemployment; 5) Conserving nature, the environment, and resources; 6) Advancing culture; 7) Elevate the image of the nation; 8) Cultivate a sense of love for the motherland; 9) Strengthening the identity and unity of the nation, and 10) Strengthen friendships between nations. Murphy (1985), who writes a book entitled *Tourism: A Community Approach*, defines the tourism sector as a whole of elements related to tourists, tourist destinations, travel, industry, and others, which are the result of tourists' trips to tourist destinations throughout the journey is not permanent. Fennell (1999) states that tourism is a system that includes tourists and the services provided (in the form of facilities, attractions, transportation, and accommodation) to satisfy and support their travel. According to the WTO in agenda 21 for the travel and tourism industry states: Sustainable tourism development meets the needs of tourists and people of tourist destinations while protecting and developing opportunities in the future. Viewed as something that leads to management, all resources in a way that economic, social, and aesthetic needs can be met alongside cultural integrity, essential ecological processes, biological diversity, and life-supporting systems are maintained. The strategic issues in Sustainable Tourism are as follows (Hidayat, M., 2011:37):

1. Increase the responsibility of Corporate Stakeholders;
2. Produce a suitable Form of tourism;
3. To sustain Social and Cultural Resources;
4. To sustain the Natural Environment;
5. The need for an effective plan for Tourism Destination Regional Planning;
6. The role of "Carrying Capacities" and indicators in Sustainable Tourism.
7. Avoiding conflicts;
8. Increased community engagement;
9. Briefing for the future.

3. METHOD

This research uses a quantitative approach method which is an approach to testing the objective theory by testing the relationship between variables. This variable can be measured using instruments so that the number of data can be analyzed using statistical procedures (Creswell, 2014).

The population in this study was a regional apparatus organization (OPD) in Banyuwangi that entered the management following the Decree of the Regent of Banyuwangi Number: 188/51/KEP/429.011/2018 concerning the Banyuwangi's Healthy Regency Technical Development Team in the healthy tourism order as many as four respondents and members of the Banyuwangi Healthy Forum according to the Decree of the Banyuwangi Regent Number 188/26/KEP/429.011/2019 concerning the Healthy Regency Forum in Banyuwangi as many as 11 people and the head of the Kelompok Sadar Wisata (a committee which is consist of local people who concern about tourism) was 62 people, so the population of this study was 77 respondents.

This study took a sample of the study with a Judgement (purposive) sampling technique. This research raised about healthy tourism development policies in Banyuwangi; the respondents in this study were devoted to respondents who were experts and knew actually about the healthy tourism development policy. Why do not all respondents in the Banyuwangi local government know about the policy? The respondents in this study were: The Regional Development Planning Agency of Banyuwangi; Banyuwangi District Health Office; Culture and Tourism Office of Banyuwangi; Forum Banyuwangi Sehat; Tourism Awareness Group (Pokdarwis).

The research locations are natural tourist destinations in Banyuwangi which are in the top 10 number of visitors in 2020 are ten tourist destinations: Boom Marina Tourism; Red Island Beach; Catalan Beach; Alas Purwo National Park; Tamansari Village; Djawatan; Religious Tourism of the Tomb of Datuk Abd Bauzir; Ijen Crater; Meru Betiri National Park; and Grand Watu Dodol (GWD).

The analysis uses the Analytic Network Process (ANP), a development of the AHP method. ANP allows interaction and feedback from elements in the cluster (inner dependence) and between clusters (external dependence). ANP is a method of solving an unstructured problem and the dependence of relationships between its elements.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Banyuwangi Tourist Destinations

Banyuwangi, located at the tip of the island of Java, has exotic beaches as the destination that will provide its own travel experience for its visitors. This study is focused on health tourism development policies. Pokdarwis is in charge of maintaining the sustainability and progress of its tourist destinations. In addition, this research also takes the location of tourist destinations that have become icons in Banyuwangi, which has an increasing number of tourist visits in line

with the improvement of the services provided by these destinations. The ten tourist destinations that occupied the highest ten visitors in 2021 are as follows.

Figure 5: Portrait of Tourist Destinations Banyuwangi Regency Culture and Tourism Office, 2021

Marina Boom	Plengkung Alas Purwo	Destinasi Pulau Merah
Tamansari Tourism Village	Teluk Hijau Merubetiri	Grand Watu Dodol
Djawatan	Cacalan Beach	Kawah Ijen
		Religious Tour of Datuk Ibrahim's Tomb

Based on Figure 5, the ten tourist destinations with the highest number of visitors consist of natural attractions consisting of beaches, trees, and mountains. In addition, there are tourist villages and religious tourism in the form of tombs that many pilgrims visit.

4.1 Targets and Achievements of Healthy Tourism Development in Banyuwangi Regency Macro

Analyzing targets and achievements of healthy tourism development in Banyuwangi Regency was macro-filled by expert respondents from Bappeda, Health Office, Culture and Tourism Office, and Banyuwangi Sehat Forum.

Figure 6: Graph of the Number of Domestic and Foreign Tourist Visits (Soul)

(Source: Banyuwangi Regency Culture and Tourism Office, 2021)

Figure 6 shows that from 2013 to 2019, tourist visits to Banyuwangi have increased. When the Covid-19 pandemic hit Banyuwangi around February 2020, tourist destinations closed to break the transmission chain of Covid 19. This phenomenon caused the number of visits in 2020 and 2021 to decline of visits in 2020 by -44% and in 2021 a decline of -39%. The results of the analysis of the targets and achievements of the development of Healthy Tourism in Banyuwangi are as follows.

Table 1: Targets and Achievements of Healthy Tourism Development in Banyuwangi

No	Indikator	Score			
		Bappeda	Dinkes	Disbudpar	FBS
1	Travel and Health Information	450	350	400	300
2	Tourism Facilities	350	350	350	350
3	Tourist Attractions	400	400	400	400
4	Health services	350	350	350	350
5	Supporting facilities	500	500	500	500
6	Society	500	500	500	500
Amount		2550	2450	2500	2400
Percentage		85,0	81,7	83,3	80,0

Source: Data Primer, processed

Based on Table 1 the average obtained from all expert respondents was 82.5%, meaning that macro-wise the Development of Healthy Tourism in Banyuwangi has reached the target as a regency that deserves to be categorized as health tourism. Although, it is still needed to have to carry out the right strategies to improve the quality of each tourist destination in

Banyuwangi, which consists of Natural Tourism, Artificial Tourism, Religious Tourism, and Cultural Tourism which requires synergy from all Banyuwangi people to maintain the continuity or sustainability of tourism in Banyuwangi.

4.2 Targets and Achievements of Healthy Tourism Development in 10 Tourist Destinations with the Highest Visits

The analysis of targets and achievements of healthy tourism development in 10 tourist destinations with the highest visits data in 2020 was filled by each tourism awareness group / DTW manager.

Figure 7: Graph of Number of Tourist Visits (Soul) (Source: Banyuwangi Regency Culture and Tourism Office, 2021)

Figure 7 show that Boom Marina Tourism has several visits that occupy the top position in 2020, which are 627,902 tourists. Although in that year, there was also an open and close system in each destination to break the spread of Covid 19, due to the ease of accessibility and amenity and services from the beach because it was open day and night, as well as a beautiful view at night, the beach were in great demand by visitors.

Figure 8 Percentage Charts of Healthy Tourism Development Score (Source: Primary Data, 2021)

Figure 8 shows that among the ten tourist destinations that have the highest number of visits in the top ten in 2020, it shows that the results of the percentage of particular indicators in the development of health tourism in tourist destination areas are by the standards of the Joint Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs and Minister of Health No. 34 of 2005 and No. 1138 / MENKES / PB / VIII / 2005 dated August 3, 2005, that the category of healthy tourism areas if the area has a minimum score value of 80%. Tourist destinations with a percentage score above 80% are Grand Watu Dodol (GWD), Tamansari Village, Catalan Beach, Red Island, and Boom Marina Tourism. At the same time, other tourist destinations such as Ijen Crater, Alas Purwo National Park, and Meru Betiri National Park have less than 80%.

4.3 Synthesis of Healthy Tourism Development with Analytic Network Process (ANP)

Inputting the ANP framework in super decision software is carried out through three (3) stages, namely:

Figure 9: Analytic Network Process (ANP) Subcriteria Design (Source: Superdecisions, 2021)

Figure 9 showed that the sub-criteria in this study were colored according to the colour of the criteria cluster to facilitate the process of making node connections. Furthermore, when connected according to the network, the weight of each indicator will be determined according to the choice of expert respondents using the make pair wise comparisons menu.

Research respondents have different opinions in determining the answers to the ANP questionnaire. Therefore, the ANP analysis in the super decision software presents the results of conclusions based on the average value (geometric mean). The overall order of priority and synthesis results for each respondent at this stage as outlined in the synthesis results in the ANP process. At this stage, it will show the overall geometric mean results to get answers from all respondents.

The inconsistency value of the test with the ANP method is the validity value of the pair wise comparison of each respondent where the value must meet the required criteria, namely with an inconsistency value of not more than 10% or 0.10. Table 2 Inconsistency Values of Cluster Goal Node Elements to Cluster Problems/Criteria, Sub Criteria, and Alternatives/Strategies

Table 2: Inconsistency Values of Cluster Goal Node Elements to Cluster Problems / Criteria, Sub Criteria, and Alternatives/Strategies

No	Cluster	Node to Cluster	Bappeda	Disbudpar	Dinkes	FBS	Geomean
	Healthy Tourism	Kriteria	0,05741	0,04277	0,05741	0,09643	0,0635
1	Travel and Health Information	sub Kriteria	0,06396	0,06396	0,06396	0,06396	0,0640
		Alternatif	0,05165	0,00675	0,01361	0,00254	0,0186
2	Tourism Facilities	sub Kriteria	0,07034	0,07034	0,07034	0,07034	0,0703
		Alternatif	0,08247	0,05156	0,05156	0,07069	0,0641
3	Tourist Attractions	sub Kriteria	0,07921	0,07921	0,07921	0,07921	0,0792
		Alternatif	0,05156	0,05156	0,02089	0,00119	0,0313
4	Health services	sub Kriteria	0,04453	0,04453	0,04453	0,04453	0,0445
		Alternatif	0,06239	0,06239	0,06239	0,08247	0,0674
5	Supporting facilities	sub Kriteria	0,08726	0,08726	0,08726	0,08726	0,0873
		Alternatif	0,05156	0,05156	0,05156	0,01361	0,0421
6	Society	sub Kriteria	0,02905	0,02905	0,02905	0,02905	0,0291
		Alternatives	0,05156	0,05156	0,05156	0,05156	0,0516

Source: Data Primer, processed

The potential for inconsistencies in respondents' answers would be even more significant if the number of elements compared increases. The value of inconsistencies in the criteria cluster, sub-criteria, and alternatives in tourism development in Banyuwangi is as follows. Table 2 indicate that the inconsistent values of pair wise comparison between elements in one cluster to another are all below 0.10 or 10%. These results show that in research on the development of health tourism in realizing sustainable development, it has been proven that the pair wise comparison answers carried out based on geomean from the four expert respondents consisting of the Health Office, Culture and Tourism Office, and Banyuwangi Bappeda, and the Banyuwangi Sehat Forum (FBS) have produced valid and consistent data.

Interpretation and analysis of healthy tourism development in realizing sustainable development in Banyuwangi from the results of a comprehensive ANP, the results of the synthesis of clusters as a whole along with the rater agreement in the health tourism development policy to realize sustainable development in Banyuwangi based on the results of the agreement of all respondents using Kendall's coefficient of concordance W (rater agreement) analysis with a high value.

This shows that the analysis of the statements of expert respondents of the Health Office, Culture and Tourism Office, Banyuwangi Regency Bappeda, and the Banyuwangi Sehat Forum have produced valid and consistent data. The synergy between policymakers and tourism awareness groups as manager of tourist destinations has a strong bond in the sustainability of economic development in Banyuwangi. The increase in the number of tourist visits must be balanced with the implementation health protocols by applying *peduli lindungi* application as a control for tourist networking to break the spread of Covid 19.

Sustainable innovation continues to be implemented in Banyuwangi, marketing using Smartphone applications. The sector, which is still very potential and optimistic about being developed in Banyuwangi, continues to be strengthened. The increase in tourist objects and attractions is one of the innovations expected to increase visitors' interest to come back and increase visitor satisfaction (Jauhariyah et al. 2019).

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Macro-wise, the development of Healthy Tourism in Banyuwangi has reached the target as a regency that deserves to be categorized as health tourism. Although, later right strategies are needed to improve the quality of each tourist destination in Banyuwangi, which consists of Natural Tourism, Artificial Tourism, Religious Tourism, and Cultural Tourism which requires synergy from all Banyuwangi people to maintain the continuity or sustainability of tourism in Banyuwangi. The synthesis of clusters, elements, and networks in determining priorities in healthy tourism development policies, especially in the conditions of the Covid-19 pandemic in Banyuwangi, shows that the policy priority of the role of the government intervention lies in the development of the tourist destination and tourist attractions so that they become tourist destinations that will be able to optimize the fulfilment of market needs where tourist destinations are one of the public goods that can boost local income. The value of the rater agreement in each cluster in Kendall's coefficient of concordance method in determining the priority of healthy tourism development policies in Banyuwangi shows that the amount of respondents' agreements is, on average, with a high value in determining policies in the development of health tourism in Banyuwangi.

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